

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MORALE CLIMATE OF THE ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

The moral climate of an organization is determined by its organizational culture. Formal, legally recorded aspects of the organization in the form of statutory goals, mission, values may diverge from the fundamental goals and content of activities and the nature of human relationships that are formed in the organization, therefore we can talk about a formal, legitimate organizational culture and a shadow or authentic organizational culture that is implemented in this organization. The moral climate in public organizations related to organic culture is determined by a set of social and ethical values shared by members of these public organizations, in state organizations related to bureaucratic organizational culture, by officially adopted laws and codes that civil servants must strictly follow. In commercial organizations, goals are achieved by creating high sustainable motivation of employees and members, including moral motivation.

Keywords: *Moral climate, organic culture, ethical doctrine, power function, moral regulation*

Introduction

An entrepreneurial organizational culture's ethical doctrine must be built on the principles of egoism, which pursues the extraction of maximum profit for each organization member. The moral principles of an organic organizational culture built on the foundations of collectivism imply the maximum achievement of equality for each team member, equal rights, and equal responsibilities.

Discussion

A bureaucratic organizational culture is dual, since it has a hierarchical organization, and the "morality of the top" and the "morality of the bottom", as is known, always differ. They are united by the maximum delegation of responsibility upwards, i.e., the irresponsible behavior of all members of the organization and the maximum concentration of power functions and responsibility in those at the top of this "pyramid of power". Therefore, the principle of the "top" is "do whatever you want", and the "bottom" is "do what the boss tells you". This state of a split, alienated, "unhappy consciousness" is most characteristic of a bureaucratic culture. Three models can describe the relationship between a superior and a subordinate:

- The subordinate considers himself a victim of circumstances in the environment or the conditions that the superior creates and completely imposes on him; therefore, the superior bears full moral responsibility for everything that happens to subordinates.

- the subordinate is an "empty vessel" acting by the role prescribed by the organization and is responsible only for the extent to which he meets the expectations or prescriptions imposed on this role in this organization;

- The subordinate is a savvy performer who can not only please the superior, but also not offend himself. This is the height of double standards, when,

as they used to say in "stagnant" times, "the superiors pretend to pay, and the subordinates pretend to work."

A participative organizational culture is built on maximum self-development for each team member. Participation depends on the competence and awareness of all organization members regarding their everyday affairs. The role of moral regulation increases, and the principle of justice becomes the key principle.

A rational attitude to the moral regulation of relationships in an organization, the institutionalization of morality give rise to the need for specific practical recommendations regarding the resolution of complex problem situations, the so-called ethical dilemmas, when a manager is forced to choose not between two identical from an ethical point of view courses of action, but must decide whether or not to do something that, although beneficial to him or the organization or both, may be considered unethical. Is it ethical, for example, to give a bribe to get a lucrative contract? Is it ethical to allow your company to place hazardous waste in a dangerous form? Is it ethical to hide information that may force a good employee to change jobs? Is it ethical to do personal business at work?

Managers and executives face such dilemmas in the relationships between superiors and subordinates and with customers, competitors, suppliers, and dispatchers. Consequently, more and more organizations need ethics training programs to help managers clarify their ethical principles and practice self-discipline when making decisions under challenging circumstances. Unfortunately, each of us can rationalize immoral behavior. We can convince ourselves that such actions are acceptable. The best way to prevent immoral actions is to recognize that this justification is based on flawed and self-serving logic. It is helpful to be aware of four common rationalizations for unethical behavior:

- Convince yourself that the behavior is not unethical or illegal;

- Excuse the behavior by claiming that you are acting in the organization's best interests or your best interests.
- Pretend that the behavior is okay because no one else will know about it;
- Hope your superiors will support and help you if things go wrong.

The organization's leaders' moral position and personal qualities play a special role in shaping its ethical climate.

Moral responsibilities of the leader:

1. Analysis of the value aspects of any problem facing the organization.
2. Control of affects and emotions - their and those around them.
3. Analysis of preferences in the organization in the categories of "awareness", "involvement", and "commitment", which are vague concepts.
4. Implementation of ethical choice: "Do not do what you want, but what you should." Six ethical models of leadership:
 - leader-protector (guardian);
 - leader-Confucian sage;
 - exponent of the idea of social equality;
 - neo-stoic leader - a sense of duty and commitment to classical ethical standards prevail;
 - leader, super-professional;
 - Charismatic leader.
5. Mastering the philosophy of noble labor.
6. Mastering the art of indifference to one's benefit.

In Georgian reality, however, it is customary to be overly loyal to the boss's actions, whose personal sympathies are regarded as a decisive factor in the well-being of the company's members.

This is the opinion of Western entrepreneurs who have opened their companies in our country.

Business etiquette

This section of the corporate ethical code is easier to control and regulate than others. Sometimes, etiquette is all that remains of administrative business ethics. Etiquette does not relate to the actual moral methods of regulating behavior, so there are no articles about it in philosophical ethical dictionaries. Strictly regulating the forms of external behavior, etiquette does not leave a person freedom of choice. In addition, the implementation of etiquette concerns only external behavior and does not affect the sphere of moral consciousness. "The more civilized people are, the more actors they are," said I. Kant.

The rules of business etiquette are generally accepted in international business communication, although they also have some national and corporate characteristics.

In an organization, business etiquette depends on what style of business communication and management (authoritarian, democratic, liberal, or permissive) is characteristic of business communication in the organization as a whole, as well as on the activities of the organization, the tastes of its management, and traditions. Specific recommendations regarding the rules of etiquette can be found in specialized literature.

Here we will cite six basic commandments of business etiquette, formulated by the American researcher, sociologist, and promoter of the rules of politeness in business communication, Jen Yager.

1. Motto: Do everything on time!

Being late not only interferes with work, but is also the first sign that a person cannot be relied upon. Sometimes being on time means not being too early, not before your boss. The main thing in your daily schedule is to be on time in the morning. If you need to be late and you know about it in advance, call the office and let your secretary or someone from your boss know.

Experts who study the organization and distribution of work time advise adding an extra 25% to the time that, in your opinion, is required to complete a given task. Remember Murphy's Law: everything takes longer than you think, and all the obstacles that can arise are sure to arise. So set aside time with a reserve for those difficulties that can be predicted.

2. Don't blab!

This principle means that you are obliged to keep the secrets of a corporation, institution, or a specific transaction as carefully as you would stay personal secrets.

Never tell anyone what you hear from a colleague, manager, or subordinate about their personal life.

3. Be kind, friendly, and welcoming!

Your clients, customers, buyers, colleagues, or subordinates can find fault with you as much as they want; it doesn't matter: you are still obliged to behave politely, friendly, and welcomingly with them. Who likes to work with people who are grumpy, suspicious, and capricious? Only a friendly attitude towards others will allow you to reach the top (which does not mean being friends with everyone you have to communicate with on duty). If everyone around you says you know how to please, you are on the right track. One of the essential elements of good manners and friendliness is the art of saying what needs to be said. You must adhere to the same principle in your actions, which are reflected in your speeches.

4. Think about others, not just yourself!

Whatever your business, the need to find out the customer's or buyer's point of view will help you advance in almost any industry - from manufacturing and publishing to medicine and telecommunications. Attention to others should be shown to customers or buyers, colleagues, superiors, and subordinates. Respect the opinions of others, and try to understand why they have formed one point of view or another. Always listen to criticism and advice from colleagues, superiors, and subordinates. Do not immediately start snapping when someone questions the quality of your work; show that you value the ideas and experience of other people. Self-confidence should not prevent you from being modest.

5. Dress appropriately!

The most important principle, which should never be forgotten, is that first of all, you should strive to fit into your environment at work, and within this environment, into the contingent of workers at your level. Some experts advise dressing for work the way

you want, and not “the way it’s supposed to be”, but it’s better not to follow this advice. Whatever your current role in the company, you need to “fit in”, but at the same time, you should look your best, i.e., dress tastefully, choose the right color scheme for your face, and carefully select accessories: from shoes to ties.

6. Speak and write correctly!

What does it mean to use the spoken and written word correctly? Everything you say and write, be it internal notes or any letters sent outside the company to anyone, should be written in good language, and all proper names should be conveyed without errors. Make sure that you never use swear words: it may happen that a conversation that you consider completely private, to your misfortune, will be involuntarily overheard by a person on whose opinion your entire career depends. If, for some reason, you repeat a third party’s swear words, either as a quote or when discussing a situation, do not use the swear word itself. There are ways to indicate that a swear word has been omitted from the text, such as using the term “expletive.”

Conclusion

“Etiquette” means the established order of behavior in a particular social sphere: court, diplomatic, military, high society, church, sports, scientific

communities, business, and management. Etiquette is a system of detailed rules of politeness, including forms of acquaintance, greeting and farewell, expression of gratitude and sympathy, speech culture, the ability to conduct a conversation, rules of behavior at the table, congratulations, gifts, etc. All these situations in business etiquette are supplemented by rules of behavior when applying for a job and changing jobs, rules of a boss’s treatment of subordinates, rules of talking on a business telephone, business correspondence, office interior design, and relations between men and women in the process of business communication.

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